

Australian Vocabularies 2022 Symposium

Australian Vocabularies Symposium 2022, 14-15 November

DAY 1: Monday. Australian Eastern Daylight Time. ([AEDT](#))

Understanding the present	
Time	Item
10:00 - 10:30	Session 1: Opening 1. Setting the Context (Steve McEachern), and Welcome to country (Paul House, ANU First Nations Portfolio). (slides / recording)
10:30 - 11:15	Session 2: Keynote: Data Commons: Knowledge infrastructure to support impactful research. (slides / recording) Speaker: Adrian Burton, Australian Research Data Commons.
11:15 - 11:30	Break 1 (Coffee)
11:30 - 12:45	Session 3 Presentations on International Vocabularies and services (15 min presentation + 5 min Q&A) 1. Barbara Magagna - I-ADOPT: a semantic broker for variable descriptions across terminologies. (abstract / slides / recording) 2. Simon Cox (CSIRO/CODATA) - Digital Representation of Units of Measure. (abstract / slides / recording) 3. Stuart Chalk (IUPAC) - The IUPAC Gold Book: Compendium of Chemical Terminology (abstract / slides / recording) 4. Marthe Klöcking (GEOROC) - Developing Vocabularies for the International OneGeochemistry Initiative: Specifying Locally, Harmonising Globally (abstract / slides / recording)
12:45 - 13:45	Break 2 (Lunch)
13:45 - 15:00	Session 4: Presentations on Vocabularies in Australia - current practices (15 min presentation + 5 min Q&A) 1. Susan Birtles (Committee on Place Names) - Place name vocabularies - examples and observations (abstract / slides / recording)

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Les Kneebone (Uni Melbourne) - Consolidating approaches: how the Public Policy Taxonomy was made (abstract / slides / recording) 3. Jens Klump (CSIRO) - Industrial Equipment Reference Data Sets - a review of structures and utility (abstract / slides / recording)
15:00 - 15:20	Break 3 (Coffee)
15:20 - 15:55	Session 5 Group brainstorm: Mapping the landscape questionnaire
15:55 - 16:00	Closing day 1: Controlled Vocabulary landscape - Kheeran

DAY 2: Tuesday. Australian Eastern Daylight Time. ([AEDT](#))

Imagining the future	
Time	Item
10:00 -10:10	Session 6: Opening Welcome to day 2, and Some Observations about the Vocabulary Landscape: Kheeran Dharmawardena (slides / recording)
10:10-10:45	Session 7: Keynote: WorldFAIR and Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges, Speaker: Simon Hodson, Executive Director, CODATA (slides / recording)
10:45-11:00	Break 1 (Coffee)
11:00-12:30	Session 8: Presentations on Strategies, systems and tools: solutions for the discovery and re-use of trusted vocabularies within and across domains (15 min presentation + 5 min Q&A) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rob Atkinson (OGC) - Role of Vocabularies in Inter-system interoperability (abstract / slides / recording) 2. Theresa Anderson (Connecting Stones/Hocone) - Speaking the same language: co-creation of inclusive vocabularies and standards for data use (abstract / slides / recording)

	<p>3. Edmond Chuc (UQ) - Use of GitHub to create and manage semantic-enabled controlled vocabularies with a case study (abstract / slides / recording)</p> <p>4. Lizzy Wenk (UNSW) - Documenting the AusTraits ontology (abstract / slides / recording)</p>
12:30-13:30	Break 2 (Lunch)
13:30-15:00	<p>Session 9 Presentations on strategies, systems and tools: solutions for the discovery and re-use of trusted vocabularies within and across domains (15 min presentation + 5 min Q&A)</p> <p>5. Siddeswara Guru (TERN) - Linked Open vocabularies for ecosystem science community (abstract / slides / recording)</p> <p>6. Jess Moore (ANU) - Unlocking health data for personal access and reuse (abstract / slides / recording)</p> <p>7. Nick Car (KurrawongAI) - The emerging, multi-layered, geo-vocabulary governance regime (abstract / slides / recording)</p> <p>8. Dougie Boyle (Uni Melbourne) - Research Terminologies Australia (Rosetta) (abstract / slides / recording)</p>
15:00-15:15	Break 3 (Coffee)
15:15-15:45	<p>Session 10: Group brainstorm: What solutions could help make vocabularies more re-usable within and across domains?</p>
15:45-16:00	<p>Session 11: Wrap up Where are we at, where to from here? Steve</p>